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Awareness and Uptake of Cervical Cancer Screening among Women in Onitsha, South-East, Nigeria

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Cervical cancer is the second commonest female malignancy in the world. It is the leading cause of gynaecological cancers in the developing countries. The cornerstone of the preventive measure is the use of cervical screening. This study was undertaken to investigate the awareness of cervical cancer screening and uptake among women in Onitsha, Anambra State, Nigeria. Data were collected using close-ended structured questionnaires. 450 questionnaires, based on completeness were analyzed. Percentages were calculated and expressed in simple descriptive statistics. Results showed that the awareness of cervical cancer screening was 160 (35.56%), while 8 (1.78%) had done the test. The reasons for not doing the test were: cost 70 (15.84%), lack of facility 70 (15.84%), lack of awareness 228 (51.58%), distance 13 (2.94%), do not think it is necessary 52 (11.76%), no reason 9 (2.04%). Majority of the respondents were traders 120 (26.67%) and students 119 (26.44%). 133 (29.56%) had secondary education, while 284 (63.11%) had tertiary education. In conclusion, the awareness was very low. The uptake was poor. Public enlightenment campaign targeting women should be instituted. Cervical cancer screening should be made affordable and available to women.

Keywords: Awareness, cervical cancer screening, uptake, Onitsha.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, cervical cancer is the second commonest female malignancy (Canavan and Doshi, 2000). It accounts for approximately 300,000 deaths annually worldwide and half a million new cases are reported each year (Anorlu, 2004; Parkin et al., 1999; Shoell et al., 1999). Approximately, 80% of these new cases come from developing countries where the disease is also the leading cause of cancer-related death among women (Sankaranayanan et al., 2001).

In Nigeria, the national incidence of cervical cancer is 250/100,000 (Adewole et al., 1997). Ogunbayo et al., (2011) reported that cervical cancer was the leading cause of gynecological cancers in Northern Nigeria, accounting for 65.7% of all gynecological cancers. This high incidence was also observed in Ibadan and Maiduguri (Nigeria) with 62.7% and 72.6% respectively (Pindiga et al., 1999; Adelus, 1978; Rafindadi et al., 1999).

This grim picture contrasts sharply with what is obtained in developed countries where the incidence and mortality are about half for the rest of world. The huge disparities in morbidity and mortality between developed and developing countries exist largely because over the last few decades, developed countries have implemented effective programme for the prevention of cervical cancer, in some countries reducing the incidence and mortality by up to 80% (Sankaranayanan et al., 2001). On the other hand, in developing countries where access to screening services for cervical cancer is often limited or non-existent, the incidence of women affected by the disease continues to exist at high levels (Vizcaino et al., 2000; Wabinga et al., 2000).

Cervical cancer, therefore, is a preventable disease. Because cervical cancer has a latent period and starts with a pre-invasive stage that is curable, it is possible to detect the disease early and take necessary steps to prevent progression to life-threatening advanced stage of the disease (Kawonga, 2003).

The cornerstone of this preventive measure is the use of cervical screening by the Papanicolaou test (pap smear). Cervical cancer screening is recommended starting at age 21 (Saslow et al., 2012). Recommendations for how often a pap smear should be done vary from once a year to once every five years, in the absence of abnormal results (Arbyn et al., 2010). Studies have shown that the participation rate in cervical cancer screening is of utmost importance for the effectiveness of a cervical cancer-screening programme (Sepulveda and Prado, 2005., Guidozi, 1996).

Cytology-based cervical cancer screening programme may be a challenge to implement in low-resource settings (Goldie et al., 2001). In an effort to curb the burden of cervical cancer in developing countries, the World

Health Organization (WHO) and the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) have established cervical cancer screening programmes by adopting an alternative screening method based on visual inspection with acetic acid (VIA) (Denny et al., 2005, Miller et al., 2003, Kahesa et al., 2012) .

This study was undertaken to investigate the awareness of cervical cancer screening and uptake among women in Onitsha, South-East, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a cross-sectional, descriptive study carried out in five different locations of Onitsha. To make sure that all the segments of the commercial town were reached we visited schools, Churches, business outlets, banks, markets.

Data were collected using close-ended structured questionnaires. The respondents were not required to write but just to tick the appropriate boxes which were provided for each number. Names were not used for identification. Coding numbers were used instead. This ensured that the identities of the individual respondent remained protected. The designed questionnaire contained information on such characteristics such as age, marital status, occupation, educational level, parity. The 458 questionnaires obtained from the study were manually sorted out to obtain the best 450 questionnaires based on the level of completeness.

Ethical Consideration

The study was approved by the Ethical Committee of the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, Anambra State University, Uli campus. The study was carried out with the help of research assistants who explained the objective of the study and the contents of the questionnaires to the respondents who willingly agreed and participated in the study. Having obtained their consent, they were assured that the data collected would be used for research purposes only.

Statistical Analysis

Percentages of relevant data were calculated and expressed in simple descriptive statistics.

RESULTS

The results showed that 119 (26.44%) of the respondents were students, 90 (20%) were civil servants, 9 (2%) were housewives, 67 (14.89%) were professionals, 120 (26.67%) were traders, while 45 (10%) were self-employed.

Those within the age range of 20 and less were 27 (6%), 179 (39.78%) were within the age range of 21-30 years. 110 (24.44%) belonged to 31-40 age range. 41-50 age range had 69 (15.33%) .51-60 age range had 31 (6.89%).20 (4.44%) belonged to 61-70 age range. 71-80 age range had 14 (3.11%).162 (36%) were single, 231 (51.33%) were married, 57 (12.67%) were widowed.29 (6.44%) had primary education, 133 (29.56%) had secondary education.284 (63.11%) had tertiary education. 4 (0.89%) had no formal education. 185 (41.11%) were nulliparous. 62 (13.78%) had a child.115 (25.56%) had two to four children. 88 (19.56%) had greater than four children.239 (53.11%) were aware of cervical cancer as a disease. 211 (46.89%) said they have not heard about cervical cancer. Their source of information on cervical cancer screening included: health care personnel 154 (64.44%), friends/relations 30 (12.55%), mass media 24 (10.04%), internet 17 (7.11%), print media/book 14 (5.86%).

Awareness of cervical cancer screening (pap smear) was 160 (35.56%).290 (64.44%) were not aware of this test.8 (1.78%) have done the test. 442 (98.22%) have not done the test. Reasons adduced for not doing the screening included cost 70 (15.84%), lack of facility 70 (15.84%), lack of awareness 228 (51.58%), distance 13 (2.94%), don't think it is necessary 52 (11.76%), no reason 9 (2.04%). 374 (83.11%) said they would like to do the test if made affordable and available.72 (16%) said they would not like to do it. 4 (0.88%) admitted somebody related to them had suffered from cervical cancer.343 (76.22%) said they did not know whether somebody related to them had suffered from cervical cancer.103 (22.89%) were not sure.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Variables	Number	Percentage (%)
Age		
20 & less	27	6.00
21-30	179	39.78
31-40	110	24.44
41-50	69	15.33
51-60	31	6.89
61-70	20	4.44
71-80	14	3.11
Marital status		
Single	162	36.00
Married	231	51.33
Widowed	57	12.67
Educational level		
Primary	29	6.44
Secondary	133	29.56
Tertiary	284	63.11
None	4	0.89
Occupation		
Student	119	26.44
Civil servant	90	20.00
House-wife	9	2.00
Professional	67	14.89
Trading	120	26.67
Self-employed	45	10.00
Parity		
Nulliparous	185	41.11
Para 1	62	13.78
Para 2-4	115	25.56
Para 5 and above	88	19.56

Table 2: Awereness of cervical cancer screening

Yes	160	35.56
No	290	64.44

Table 3: Screening uptake distribution among respondents

Yes	8	1.78
No	442	98.22

Figure 1: Reasons for not doing cervical cancer screening

Figure 2: Source of Information on cervical cancer screening

DISCUSSION

This present study focused on the awareness of cervical cancer screening and uptake among women in Onitsha. The findings showed that 35.56% were aware of this test, while 8 (1.78%) have done the test. This level of awareness is low. Worse still, the uptake is poor. The level of awareness of cervical cancer screening of 35.56% found in this study is less than 52.8% from Owerri (Ezem, 2007), 69.8% from Ilorin (Aboyeji et al., 2004), 70% from Ibadan (Ayinde et al., 1998). It is just close to 39% reported in Ghana. (Adanu, 2002). Variations may be attributed to different classes of respondents used in the study. Studies using healthcare personnel (nurses, doctors, laboratory scientists) tend to report high awareness. In this present study, respondents were drawn from the general population of women resident in Onitsha.

Ordinarily, cervical cancer is of public health significance. Unfortunately, here in Nigeria and other sub-Saharan countries health policy makers have not accorded it priority. This may be due to the perception of some people who regard cancers generally as diseases of the western world. Changes in lifestyle and urbanization have made some of the diseases previously thought to be foreign to affect our people.

The uptake of 1.78% found in this study is lower than 7.1% reported by Ezem, (2007), but higher than 0.6% reported by Eze et al., (2012). The burden of cervical cancer can not be appreciably reduced with these very low levels of uptake. The main reason adduced by the respondents for not doing the test was lack of awareness (51.58%), followed by cost (15.84%) and lack of facility (15.84%). Onitsha has no tertiary health facility. Cervical screening programmes are located mainly in tertiary medical institutions, and in some private facilities in Lagos, Abuja, and port-Harcourt. Studies done in towns with teaching hospitals may report higher uptake than those done in places without teaching hospitals.

Based on the reasons for not doing the test, 374 (83.11%) of the respondents admitted that if made available and affordable they would like to do the test. This is interesting. It has rekindled hope that with robust public enlightenment campaign targeting women coupled with availability and affordability of pap smear, the level of uptakes will significantly improve. Studies have shown that more than 40% of women in many developed countries have had a pap smear (kawonga, 2003), compared to 1.78% found in this study.

Financial resources have been channeled to combating the major scourges: Malaria, HIV and Tuberculosis (TB). This is understandable. However, effective use of available resources can help reduce the burden of cervical cancer in the country. For instance, cervical cancer screening programmes can be integrated within secondary health institution. There are many secondary health institutions in Onitsha (both government and Mission) that offer antenatal services. Existing infrastructure in these institutions can be utilized for provision of pap smears. Equally important is the education and training of service providers, to increase awareness about the screening programme and upgrade their skills. 63.11% of the respondents in this study attained tertiary level of education. Unfortunately, this high level of literacy did not translate to high utilization of cervical screening in this study. This may be attributed to financial constraints, lack of facility, and the personal feeling of not being at risk. Studies have shown that women who had attended at least primary school were more likely to attend screening in comparison with women who had never attended school, (Kahesa et al., 2012). Other studies have documented that women with low education are less knowledgeable about the need for cervical screening and have limited resources to cater for their screening attendance due to inherent cost (Bradley et al., 2004).

CONCLUSION

Cervical cancer is preventable. Cervical screening and early treatment are vital in combating this disease. The level of awareness in this present study is very low. The uptake is poor. These should be addressed in order to reduce the incidence of cervical cancer in our country. A well coordinated cervical cancer screening programme targeting at risk groups (e.g. elderly women) should be instituted. If health policy makers consider widespread use of pap smear as costly and impractical, they can consider adopting an alternative screening method based on visual inspection with acetic acid (VIA). The VIA test has proven to have similar sensitivity to that of cytology but lower specificity and positive predictive value when evaluated in clinical research settings (Deodhar et al., 2012).

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